

Fig. S5. CPN20-GFP localization in chloroplasts of cotyledon mesophyll and guard cells of 30-day-old seedlings.

(A) CPN20-GFP localization in guard cells of *CPN-20-GFP/Col-0*.

(B) CPN20-GFP localization in guard cells of *CPN-20-GFP/spy-3*.

(C) CPN20-GFP localization in mesophyll cells of *CPN-20-GFP/Col-0*.

(D) CPN20-GFP localization in mesophyll cells of *CPN-20-GFP/spy-3*.

AUTO, chloroplast autofluorescence; GFP, fluorescence of the CPN20-GFP fusion protein; Merge, merged image of Auto and GFP.